

Fractal-Network Architecture of Public Authority under Extreme Spatial and Climatic Conditions: A Cybernetic Approach

Vladimir N. Bogdanov*

Polytechnic Institute (Branch) of North-Eastern Federal University of M.K. Ammosov
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Abstract

The paper investigates deep systemic deformations of the institutional model separating state power and local self-government, which manifest under the specific conditions of the Far North and the Arctic zone of the Russian Federation. In the first part of the study, based on the methodology of general systems theory, a detailed empirical analysis of four key dysfunctions of decentralized management is carried out: technological fragmentation of unified life-support contours, legal uncertainty of balance sheet ownership, temporal-spatial blindness of unified state procurement regulations, and degradation of municipal unitary enterprises under the influence of market performance indicators (The Economics). It is proved that the artificial quantization of the managerial field and the withdrawal of investment resources from the local level lead to an exponential increase in the system's coordination costs and the physical destruction of critical infrastructure.

In the second part of the article, as a constructive alternative, the author substantiates the fractal-network architecture of public administration, which integrates the principles of structural recursion of complex systems with the dynamic matrix model of the input-output balance developed by the cybernetic school of N. I. Veduta — E. N. Veduta. Within the framework of the proposed approach, the basic concept of the Minimum Infrastructural Quantum (MIQ) is introduced, mathematically formalized, and operationalized as an indivisible column vector of the territory's resource stability. A three-stage iterative algorithm for multi-level coordination of plans by the method of successive approximations is described, the optimal design of the decision-making entity is determined (including the expert control loop and the local veto power of District Councils of Deputies), and a Higher Attestation Commission (VAK)-oriented system of management efficiency criteria is proposed, shifting the target function from cost surrogates to the parameters of reproduction of human potential and free time of the population. In conclusion, a set of measures to mitigate technological and bureaucratic risks of the transition period, including a roadmap for implementing experimental legal regimes, is proposed.

*ORCID: 0009-0005-2237-362X. Polytechnic Institute (Branch) of North-Eastern Federal University of M.K. Ammosov, Mirny, Sakha Republic (Yakutia), Russian Federation

Keywords: public authority, local self-government, Far North, Arctic zone of the Russian Federation, fractal-network architecture, cybernetic approach, dynamic input-output balance, Veduta model, minimum infrastructural quantum.

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